

**DURABILITY OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS
IN A MARINE ENVIRONMENT
A Fracture Mechanics Approach.**

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents some results from a joint programme to examine the long term durability of composites for marine applications. In particular the application of fracture mechanics tests is described which enabled the changes in toughness of thermoset and thermoplastic matrix composites immersed in water to be quantified. A comparison is made with more traditional test methods for following moisture induced degradation. Thermoplastics can offer significant advantages for marine applications but great care is required in optimising such composite systems.

Key words : Marine, Glass fibre, Epoxy, Vinyl ester, PPS, Polypropylene, Sea water, Distilled water, Mode I, Mode II.

1. INTRODUCTION

Marine applications represent a large proportion of the fibre reinforced composites market, on structures as diverse as pleasure boats, surf boards and nuclear submarines (1,2). The common factor in these applications is the necessity to resist the marine environment, and much work has been directed towards characterization of composite degradation in water. However, while large amounts of data have been collected on moisture diffusion and residual properties (e.g. (3)), the influence of moisture on one of the most common composite failure modes, delamination, has rarely been studied using tests other than the short beam shear test, whose validity is questionable (4). Some toughness data exist and Marom recently reviewed environmental effects on fracture properties (5) but as fracture mechanics tests for measuring delamination resistance have only recently been developed to a standard level, many published values have been found to be geometry dependent, since fibre bridging effects (which contribute largely to quoted propagation values of G_{IC}) frequently depend on specimen thickness. The uncertainty in measured values has been eased recently, as after detailed studies by the European Structural Integrity Society (ESIS), the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) and other groups, protocols for mode I, mode II and mixed mode testing are now available (6,7).

The most common fabrication technique in the marine industry is hand lay-up, using glass fibre reinforced polyester, but the newly-available glass reinforced thermoplastic preregs appear quite attractive (recyclable, low toxicity, virtually infinite shelf-life). Little information is available on the environmental degradation resistance of such materials but the inert nature of polymers such

as polypropylene suggests that if the fibre-matrix interface is optimised they could become ideal candidates for marine structures. This paper describes part of work undertaken in collaboration between Ifremer, FAU and EPFL to examine the potential of these and other new materials. The materials and test methods are briefly described first. Then some important considerations in determination of baseline data are presented. Examples of weight gain after immersion of resins and composites are then shown. Finally, the influence of immersion on the fracture properties of thermosetting and thermoplastic composites is illustrated.

2. MATERIALS & EXPERIMENTAL METHODS.

Within this study a large range of thermoset and thermoplastic materials reinforced with carbon, polyethylene and glass fibres have been examined using various experimental techniques (physico-chemical, mechanical, vibration, ultrasonic wave speed measurements and fracture mechanics tests). Given the limited space available only some selected examples are presented here, Table 1.

Table 1. Materials considered in the experimental programme ($V_f = 0$ signifies neat resin).

MATRIX	E glass fibre V_f	Supplier	Fabrication
<i>Thermosets</i>			
Epoxy SR1500	0 and 30%	Sicomim	Contact 20°C
Epoxy 5216	54%	BASF	Prepreg 140°C
Vinyl ester (epoxy-based) 411-45	0 and 30%	Dow Chemicals	Contact 20°C
<i>Thermoplastics</i>			
PPS Polyphenylene sulfide	0 and 53%	Phillips Petroleum	Prepreg 330°C
PP Polypropylene	35-38%	ICI "Plytron"	Prepreg 185°C

The composites were studied using the following experimental methods :

- Moisture pick-up. Measured by weight change of square specimens (50 mm by 50 mm) immersed in water at different temperatures for up to 6 months.
- Transverse tensile tests, on specimens 25 mm by 230 mm.
- 3 point and 4 point flexural tests, following ASTM standards, (length/thickness ratios of 16 and 5).
- K_{Ic} measurements on unreinforced resins, using the ESIS protocol (8) on single edge notch bend specimens.
- Mode I tests on double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens (9).
- Mode II tests on end notch flexure (ENF) specimens (10).

These mode I and mode II tests were performed and evaluated following the latest ESIS protocol (7). Specimens were nominally 5 mm thick and contained 12 μ m thick aluminium foil starter defects at beam mid-thickness.

3. APPLICABILITY OF THE FRACTURE MECHANICS APPROACH

In order to assess the applicability of the fracture mechanics approach to materials manufactured by hand lay-up, and to determine geometric limitations of such an approach in the light of low specimen stiffness, a preliminary study was performed. Part of this study, described in more detail elsewhere (9), included examination of the influence of starter defect thickness, interface ply orientation and specimen thickness. For example, for a quasi-unidirectional glass/epoxy (88% of fibres in the propagation direction), as specimen thickness is increased from 6 to 8 to 10 plies of reinforcement (4.4 to 7.5 mm in thickness) mode I initiation values remained constant within experimental scatter but propagation values increased from 1.2 to 1.5 to 1.9 kJ/m^2 . Above this thickness crack tip blunting caused increased initiation values, an unstable initial jump and unstable propagation.

The results from these initial studies were used to define the appropriate test geometries and starter defects. In certain cases the mode II specimens were plasticized by water immersion to the

extent that failures initiated on the compression side rather than by crack propagation, so slightly thicker specimens would have been preferable, but the thickness must be minimised to allow diffusion of water to the beam centre and crack tip region within a reasonable time.

4. BASELINE DATA : INFLUENCE OF FABRICATION PARAMETERS.

The study of the influence of the marine environment on material properties requires long exposure periods. Before fully investing in such a programme it is important to establish the reliability of baseline data and in particular to assess the influence of fabrication procedures on the material properties. This has been done for both thermoset and thermoplastic composites and the details will be reported elsewhere. However, to emphasize the importance of fabrication parameters two examples are shown below for :

- a thermoset matrix composite, glass/epoxy produced by hand lay-up, and
- a semi-crystalline thermoplastic matrix composite, glass/PP press-formed.

4.1. Influence of post-cure on epoxy composite properties.

If the epoxy used for moulding by hand lay-up, (SR1500), is not post-cured then crosslinking will continue at room temperature and, as shown in Figure 1, the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the composite will gradually increase with time to reach an asymptotic value. A post-cure of at least 6 hours at 60°C is therefore recommended by the material suppliers to stabilize the resin. The influence of post-cure on the composite strength and fracture properties is shown in Table 2.

Figure 1. Increase in T_g with time at RT for glass/epoxy, (SR1500, measured by DSC, no post-cure)

Table 2. Influence of 8h 60°C post-cure on properties of E-glass/epoxy SR 1500.

PROPERTY	Change after post-cure, as percentage of as-moulded values.
τ_{13} (ILSS)	+ 4%
σ_f (flexure)	- 2%
G_{Ic} , NL	0%
G_{IIc} , NL	- 15 to -30%

The non-linear initiation values were measured directly from the starter films. It is apparent that post-cure has little influence on the properties of this composite, except for the mode II delamination resistance.

4.2. Influence of cooling rate on glass/polypropylene composite properties.

The structure and properties of semi-crystalline polymers are strongly influenced by fabrication conditions. In particular the rate of cooling after moulding will determine the degree of crystallinity, spherulite size and the fracture behaviour. Panels were manufactured using three cooling conditions; turning off the press, water cooling and transferring to a cold press. These resulted in mean cooling rates over the range 185 to 60°C of 0.23, 2.6 and 55 K/min. The influence on delamination resistance is considerable and is shown in Table 3 and Figure 2. Mode I values are those corresponding to the propagation plateau, while the mode II values were obtained on ENF specimens and characterize the propagation directly from the starter film, using a 5% change in compliance as the fracture criterion.

Figure 2. Fracture toughnesses of glass/polypropylene. Mode I (DCB) & Mode II (ENF)

The slowest cooling rate resulted in large spherulitic structure and relatively low toughness values. All subsequent tests were therefore performed on panels cooled at the fastest rate.

Table 3 Glass/PP Influence of cooling rate on delamination resistance. (Standard deviations in brackets)

Cooling rate °C/min.	Crystallinity %	G_{Ic} kJ/m ² (Propagation.)	G_{IIc} kJ/m ² 5%
0.23	65	0.795 (0.090)	0.320 (0.055)
2.6	61	1.630 (0.180)	1.595 (0.120)
55	50	2.930 (0.175)	1.515 (0.240)

5. INFLUENCE OF MOISTURE.

5.1. Moisture pick-up.

Examples of curves showing the weight gains of some of the resins and composites considered are given in Figure 3. The specimens were immersed in distilled water, as it has been found to be more detrimental than salt water. Results are shown for postcured materials but results for the non-postcured material were virtually identical at these temperatures.

Figure 3. Moisture pick-up in distilled water for resins and composites.
(a) 50°C square specimens, (b) 70°C ENF specimens

Curves such as those in Figure 3 contain much information and many authors have discussed the applicability of different diffusion models, the validity of accelerated aging, the relation between resin and composite diffusion and the reversibility of water-induced effects (eg. ref. 3). Most of these authors have concentrated on thermoset composites, particularly high performance epoxies, but even for those materials many questions remain unanswered. There is not sufficient space to discuss the curves in detail here and only a few general comments will be made.

- the diffusion kinetics of distilled water in vinyl ester are much slower than those for the epoxy studied here, and saturation weight gain is lower,
- the glass/epoxy composite picks up moisture more slowly than the unreinforced epoxy resin,
- glass/PP picks up considerably less water than the epoxy composite under the same conditions and reaches saturation after 1 month at 70°C.

5.2. Influence of a marine environment.

Thermosets.

The unreinforced epoxy and vinyl ester resins were tested after different periods of immersion in distilled water at 50°C. The results shown in Table 4 are for tests performed after one month of immersion on as-moulded (not post-cured) specimens.

Table 4. Resin fracture toughness K_{Ic} after one month immersion in distilled water. (standard deviations in brackets)

Resin	Moisture pick-up, %	K_{Ic} (MPa \sqrt{m})
Epoxy SR1500		
Dry	0	0.97 (0.09)
After Immersion		
- at 20°C	0.7	1.26 (0.66)
- at 50°C	2.3	2.20 (0.24)
Vinyl ester 411-45		
Dry	0	0.82 (0.09)
After Immersion		
- at 20°C	0.5	0.96 (0.14)
- at 50°C	0.7	1.08 (0.07)

Composites with these resins and the same quasi-unidirectional fibres (post-cured at 60°C) were tested in mode I after 2 months immersion in distilled water at 60°C and the results are shown below in the form of percentage property reductions compared with the properties of the dry composites. Initiation was measured from the starter film.

Table 5. Influence of 2 months immersion in distilled water at 60°C on strength and mode I fracture properties of post-cured specimens, presented as percentages of dry specimen values.

Composite	Weight gain %	τ_{13} (ILSS)	σ_f (3 point bend)	G_{Ic} (NL) DCB
Glass/Epoxy SR1500	1.1	- 45%	- 33%	+ 76%
Glass/Vinyl ester 411-45	0.4	- 46%	- 50%	+ 47%

For these relatively low fibre volume fraction composites (Table 1) the plasticization of the matrix dominates the mode I behaviour (propagation values also increased in similar ratios) while the degradation of the fibre-matrix interface governs the shear and flexural test behaviour.

A more detailed study has been performed using the ENF mode II test (10) on the same post-cured SR1500 epoxy matrix composites, and some results are shown in Figure 4. This test is sensitive to the interface integrity and was therefore chosen as it is a more severe test of environmental attack than the mode I configuration. The values for each condition represent the mean of six specimens which were precracked in mode II. There is a small initial rise in mode II fracture toughness for 20°C immersion, which may reflect plasticisation. The higher temperature conditions show a reduction due to fibre-matrix interface degradation. After 5 months at 50°C the drop in G_{IIc} is about 30% .

Figure 4. Glass/Epoxy Mode II fracture toughness, (NL).
Coefficients of variation between 4 and 17%.

Thermoplastics.

Two thermoplastic matrix composites will be discussed here. The first, a glass reinforced PPS material, was studied using the transverse tensile test which revealed a fibre-matrix interface very susceptible to degradation by water (11,12). Thus although the PPS polymer gains less than 0.02% by weight and the fibre reinforced composite picks up less than 0.2% by weight at saturation this is sufficient to severely degrade the fibre-matrix interface. The PPS composite lost 65% of its transverse modulus and 85% of its strength. For comparison, after the same exposure an epoxy composite (5216 in Table 1) showed a slightly increased modulus and a 50% decrease in strength.

In the following part of the study glass/PP composite specimens precracked in mode II were examined. G_{IIc} data for glass/PP composites subjected to different aging treatments are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Glass/Polypropylene
Mode II fracture toughness, NL

It is apparent that the loss in mode II fracture toughness is more severe for glass/polypropylene than for glass/epoxy, see Figures 4 and 5. After 1 month at 70°C the value of G_{IIc} is reduced by 50% for the thermoplastic composite, in spite of a much lower moisture weight gain than the epoxy composite under the same conditions (Figure 3b). These results indicate both the importance of the glass fibre/matrix interface and also the unsuitability of weight gain values as a material screening parameter.

6. CONCLUSIONS

▷ The weight gain of composites after immersion in water is not a useful screening method for environmental degradation resistance. Even if the saturation weight gain is as low as 0.2% the composite interface may be severely degraded.

▷ Fracture mechanics tests are an essential complement to traditional test methods to determine residual composite properties, as the mixed stress states generated in commonly-used flexural tests can be misleading in predicting long term structural response.

▷ The influence of absorbed moisture on delamination resistance of composites with a low fibre volume fraction is dependent on the loading mode. Competition between matrix plasticisation and interface degradation can lead to an increase in mode I and a decrease in mode II fracture toughness for a given moisture content. In order to assess realistic loading cases a complete mixed mode characterization is therefore necessary.

▷ Thermoplastics such as glass/polypropylene are potentially very attractive for marine applications. However, further work is required to develop the durability of fibre-matrix interfaces in these materials.

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